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**LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS ABOUT
BACHELOR IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE COURSE
AND THE OPPORTUNITIES UPON TAKING IT: A BASIS FOR
PROMOTIONAL STRATEGIES**

A Thesis

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Bachelor in Library and Information Science

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CERTIFICATION AND APPROVAL SHEET

This thesis, **LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS ABOUT BACHELOR IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE COURSE AND THE OPPORTUNITIES UPON TAKING IT: A BASIS FOR PROMOTIONAL STRATEGIES** prepared and submitted by **ANGELICA CAMEJA, JHUNE CAPULE, ALLYSON MAE COLOMA, LAURICE AUDREY CRUZ, CHINEAH DAMPIOS, TRICIA ANN RHINE DE ROXAS, and RIZA DELA CRUZ** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, BACHELOR IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE has been examined and recommended for Oral Examination.

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Polytechnic University of the Philippines

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CERTIFICATION OF ORIGINALITY

This is to certify that the research work presented in this thesis/dissertation, **Level Of Awareness Of Grade 12 Students About Bachelor In Library And Information Science Course And The Opportunities Upon Taking It: A Basis For Promotional Strategies** for the degree Bachelor in Library and Information Science at the Polytechnic University of the Philippines embodies the result of original and scholarly work carried out by the undersigned. This dissertation does not contain words or ideas taken from published sources or written works that have been accepted as basis for the award of a degree from any other higher education institution except when proper referencing and acknowledgment were made.

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ABSTRACT

Title : Level of Awareness of Grade 12 Students About Bachelor in Library and Information Science Course and the opportunities upon taking it: a basis for promotional strategies

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In this digital age, wherein information is easily accessed online, librarians are thought to be a fading profession and there is only a small percentage of graduating high school students who would consider taking the Bachelor in Library and Information Science program or course. In this research, the problem to be addressed is the level of awareness of Grade 12 students regarding the program and all it entails, how their schema about the program affect their willingness to take the program, and, since this aims to be a basis of promotional strategies, what promotional strategies would the students prefer in order to get to know the program, profession, career opportunities and everything else about it. Although there are many students who are aware of the program, it is still not a basis of their willingness to take the program, and only a small number of the Grade 12 respondents are considering taking the course as a career choice in college.

Keywords: Librarians, Bachelor in Library and Information Science, Level of Awareness, Schema, Librarianship

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CERTIFICATION AND APPROVAL SHEET	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iii
CERTIFICATION OF ORIGINALITY	v
ABSTRACT	vi
Chapter 1	2
Background of the Study.....	2
Table 1: Number of Enrollees in each of the PUP College of Education Programs	4
Theoretical Framework	5
<i>Bartlett’s Schema Theory</i>	5
<i>John Holland’s Theory of Career Choice</i>	6
Conceptual Framework.....	8
Figure 1: A study paradigm for determining the level of awareness of Grade 12 students about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program.....	8
Statement of the Problem	9
Scope and Delimitation	10
Significance of the Study.....	10
Definition of Terms.....	12
Chapter 2	13
Career Decision Making.....	13
Career Decision Based on Sex	14
Gender Stereotype in Librarianship.....	15
Students’ Perception and Knowledge of the LIS Program, Librarians, and the Librarianship Profession.....	16
Student’s Awareness and Motivation on LIS	17
Synthesis	19
Chapter 3	21
Research Design	21
Population, Techniques and Sample Size	21
Description of the Respondents	22
Research Instrumentation	22
Data Gathering Procedure	23
Chapter 4	26
Figure 2: Profile of the Respondents According to Sex	26

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Figure 3: Track/Strand of the Respondents.....	27
Table 2.1: Level of Awareness of Grade 12 Students About Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) Program in Terms of Curriculum	28
Figure 4.1: Visual Interpretation of Table 2.1	28
Table 2.2: Level of Awareness of Grade 12 Students About Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) Program in Terms of Related Career Opportunities (based on CMO 24 s. 2015).....	30
Figure 4.2: Visual Interpretation of Table 2.2	31
Figure 5: Librarianship-related statements that the respondents agree with.....	33
Figure 6: Respondents considering on pursuing BLIS after answering the questionnaire	36
Table 3: Relationship between the Level of Awareness of the Respondents and their Willingness of Pursuing the Program	37
Figure 7: Overall Ranking of students' preferred promotional materials	38
Chapter 5.....	42
Summary of Findings	42
Conclusions	42
Recommendations	44
APPENDIX A	47
Letters.....	47
APPENDIX B	54
Survey Questionnaire	54
APPENDIX C	58
Project Proposal	58
APPENDIX D	60
Grammarians Certification	60
APPENDIX.....	61
Bionote	61
References.....	64

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING

Background of the Study

Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) is a course that revolves and focuses on the documentation of the records of stories and memories, including history and knowledge on specific subject matters. Librarians and other Library and Information Science (LIS) specialists are responsible for looking after library materials. They are tasked to collect, organize, preserve, and provide access to materials to benefit those who need the knowledge they contain (IOWA School of Library and Information Science, 2022). Therefore, BLIS program is important as it deals with what everyone needs - information - be it for their research, personal purposes, assignments, etc. It also provide the students with the necessary knowledge and skills in managing library operations, systematizing the organization, conservation, preservation, and restoration of books, historical and cultural documents, and other intellectual property, as well as the integration of information technology and management information systems for efficient management, use, and delivery of learning resources and services (College of Computing Sciences and Information Technology, 2022).

Throughout the years, the responsibilities of librarians were constantly expanding. While continuing their traditional role of curating and providing access to information, librarians are now actively facilitating the learning and research process as well (AIP Publishing, 2020). The ways and extent to which librarians can aid in research promotion vary greatly. In a study conducted by AIP Publishing (2020), over 80% of survey respondents' libraries are actively engaged in helping researchers with promotion.

In addition, according to the Pew Research Center's Internet & American Life

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Project, many library patrons want to see libraries' digital services expand, but they also believe that print books are still important in the digital age. (Pew Research Center, 2013) Therefore having easy access to Information or data is a must, as it is required to meet the tremendous needs of all potential users in this digital era (Krishnan, Sabanayagam, & Surianarayanan, 2009).

Despite the need for additional librarians, only a few people consider taking BLIS due to several factors. One factor the researchers are looking into is the lack of understanding about the program and related career opportunities resulting in lack of interest and deeming it as a boring course (Abban, 2019). In addition, due to absence of knowledge and understanding of the program, people tend to create different schema about the librarianship field which can affect how they perceive the program and related career opportunities (Abban & Saah, 2021). Aside from the previously stated point, our society is a big contributor in affecting students' perspectives about a certain career path, like associating a certain career to a specific sex. Having a few people to be considered as a career model in the field of librarianship (Tabassum & Nayak, 2021), young people would not consider librarianship as their first choice or would not consider it at all.

To show that BLIS is not that popular among students, the researchers gathered the enrollment data of PUP College of Education (COED) from A.Y 2022-2023. Despite ranking 5th in PUP COED, the percentage is small compared to – maybe – other programs from different colleges. Since not all students are aware of the career opportunities of the program, some students, like in the case of the researchers' class, choose to take the program mostly because they are influenced by their love for books (Abban, 2019).

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Table 1: Number of Enrollees in each of the PUP College of Education Programs

Program	Enrollees	Percentage
Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education Major Information and Communication Technology (BTLEDICT)	364	14.85%
Bachelor in Secondary Education Major in English (BSEDEN)	342	13.95%
Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED)	281	11.46%
Bachelor in Secondary Education Major in Mathematics (BSEDMT)	249	10.16%
Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS)	224	9.14%
Bachelor in Secondary Education Major in Filipino (BSEDFL)	182	7.43%
Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education Major in Home Economics (BTLEDHE)	173	7.06%
Bachelor in Secondary Education Major in Social Studies (BSEDSS)	164	6.69%
Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Science (BSEDSC)	154	6.28%
Bachelor of Early Childhood Education (BECED)	129	5.26%
Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education Major in Industrial Arts (BTLEDIA)	108	4.41%

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education Major in Food & Service Management (BTVTEDFS)	81	3.30%
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This study aims to introduce and promote BLIS program to students, specifically, Grade 12 learners by informing them about the program, its curriculum and goals, related career opportunities, and its role to society. In line with the said purpose, the researchers also want to measure the level of awareness – including prejudice or misconception they may have – of the students about the program to know the scope of the future promotional materials.

Theoretical Framework

Bartlett's Schema Theory

Sir Frederic Charles Bartlett is primarily mentioned as the major researcher who proposed the Schema theory in support of Jean Piaget's concept. This theory states that people's minds tend to process acquired information by creating categorized concepts (schema). These schemata are created from experiences and existing knowledge. Other studies claim that gaining added information and experiences refine the existing schema that people have (Widmayer, n.d.).

There are various key elements that can describe a schema. First, a schema can develop without an individual knowing or noticing that they had done so. Second, it can also be ingrained and stabilize over a long period of time. Third, an individual uses schema to organize chunks of information and data that are considered vital and important. Fourth, they can be accumulated from different experiences (Pappas, 2014). Schemata include stereotypes, which can affect how people process the information given to them, such as in decision making.

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

The researchers used this theory to identify the image, stereotypes, misconceptions, or prior knowledge of the respondents about the librarianship course and how it could affect their level of awareness with regards to it. With that knowledge, the researchers would be able to determine what topics could be touched when planning the initial steps for, and as basis for, promotional strategies. By integrating this theory into the level of awareness, the researchers could figure out the way they see librarians job affect what they think they work on.

John Holland's Theory of Career Choice

Image source: <https://runninginaforest.wordpress.com/2015/01/14/john-hollands-theory-of-career-choice-theories-every-careers-adviser-should-know/>

This theory basically means that people want to have jobs or take on careers with people like us. John Holland discusses in his theory that in choosing a career, most people prefer jobs which they feel comfortable with others with. That is, people prefer jobs or careers that they can be around people who are similar to them. People tend to choose environments where they could hone and use their skills and express themselves while taking on problems and taking on their roles in these specific jobs or careers. In relation, Holland's theory fits people into six personality types which are categorized in the acronym RIASEC, which stands for realistic (i.e. pilot, horticulturalist, farmer, engineer etc.), investigative (i.e. marine scientist, chemist, zoologist, dentist etc.), artistic (i.e. artist,

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illustrator, writer, instrument player, fashion designer etc.), social (i.e. teacher, police officer, social worker, nurse etc.), enterprising (i.e. lawyer, politician, accountant, business owner etc.), and conventional (i.e. secretary, officer worker, librarian, bank clerk, receptionist etc.) With this theory, Holland has defined and identified six basic work environments that corresponds to each personality type (Holland's theory, 2019).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: A study paradigm for determining the level of awareness of Grade 12 students about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program.

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This model shows the process that will be followed throughout the research. This will help the researchers reach a particular conclusion to be used as a basis for a promotional strategy.

Statement of the Problem

This research sought to identify the level of awareness of Grade 12 students and how much of this awareness affects their perception or schema of the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) and Librarianship in general. The researchers sought to identify the answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Sex
 - b. Strand
2. What is the level of awareness of Grade 12 students about librarianship in terms of:
 - a. Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) curriculum
 - b. Career opportunities (based on CMO 24 s. 2015)
3. What are the prejudices of Grade 12 students about Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) and librarianship?
4. What is the relationship between the prejudice of Grade 12 students about Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) and pursuing the course?
5. Based on the findings, what promotional strategies could be proposed by the researchers?

Scope and Delimitation

Due to the limitations and restrictions imposed during the pandemic, this study will utilize convenience sampling to target Senior High school Students, specifically grade 12 students (A.Y. 2022-2023), from various schools and universities in the Philippines who are willing to participate in the survey. The researchers will indeed touch some numerous factors that may influence career decision making, but because this study focuses heavily on the level of awareness of Grade 12 students towards the librarianship course, this study will only be looking into the bird's eye view of these factors that affect career decision making. The researchers will then have the respondents answer questions through Microsoft Forms. From the research title itself, this study is only a basis for promotional strategies, intending it to be a reference for future improvement of the current promotional strategies. Thus, this study does not include the actual execution of the promotion.

Significance of the Study

The relevance of this study is to determine whether Senior High school learners, especially Grade 12 students, know about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program and the related career opportunities it entails. The results of this study will be of great benefit to the following:

Grade 12 learners and their parents:

As Grade 12 learners are the ones more susceptible to career decision making, and as the respondents, they are the main benefactors of this study. The respondents may inform their parents of the things they may acquire through this study. Parents and students may learn about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program's curriculum, goals, and career opportunities that can somehow debunk misconceptions about librarianship.

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) students and faculty:

They will understand why other students are not aware of the program, the aspects of the program, related career opportunities, and librarianship, in general. Learning the reasons behind this will help them create an effective promotional strategy in the future.

Future researchers:

This study can serve as a basis for future researches that are related to the level of awareness of the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program. The study can also help determine actions or activities that can be implemented to improve other students' perceptions of the program, like the promotional strategies that will serve as the output of this study.

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Definition of Terms

Librarianship - The practice of using acquired knowledge after finishing a degree in Bachelor in Library and Information Science.

Misconceptions - Mistaken ideas, views, beliefs, or opinions about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science and related career opportunities.

Prejudice - Negative opinion, idea, view, or belief about librarianship without learning the facts.

Schema - Refers to an individual's stereotype about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science program and librarianship.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents the literature and studies reviewed and used by the researchers as a source of information to learn about the factors and issues that affect awareness of Grade 12 students to the BLIS program. These studies and related literature are added so that the researchers can explore and can serve as a further guide throughout the entire study. The researchers decided to inductively discuss subtopics to understand the topic better. First is career decision making which is included as an introduction into delving into the respondents' level of awareness, how it affects their knowledge of the course. And then, the researchers will connect it to the perceptions and other studies that also pertain to the level of awareness of students towards LIS, librarians, and the librarianship profession.

Career Decision Making

Career decision making is affected by a range of factors such as, socio-cultural factors – which could impact a person's beliefs – biological and cognitive factors – which influence individual thinking and organizational setting (Tabassum & Nayak, 2021). Hence, it requires undergoing a process, such as knowing oneself, exploring and understanding various career opportunities, and other external factors. Learning one's talents, capabilities, ambitions, strengths, and weaknesses can help a student decide on a career that fit them (Understand the career decision making process, n.d.). It is necessary to research one's potential course before deciding to pursue it since two out of three main reasons high school students find it hard to decide on a career are lack of information and inconsistent information (Tagay, 2015).

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

As a solution, aside from the suggestions above, a number of researchers proposed a method to make career decisions easier. Another way to consider career decision making while considering the factors also stated above, in a study by Man et al. (2022). Their research's primary purpose is to create an algorithm in the students' course selection. Due to the pandemic, the education industry has limited its efficacy in physical and online platforms, hence, the recommendation of the course selection method to further improve the online learning of the students. This system tailors a student's characteristics and preferences to a variety of programs by also looking at their characteristics, creating a balance and nonconflictual choice between the student and the career or course that may be recommended in the algorithm. (Man, Xu, Sabri, & Li, 2022).

Career Decision Based on Sex

Difference in sex is one of the factors that can affect a person's career aspirations and expectations. In a society where gender roles are embedded from early childhood – from with the influence of toys, media content, environment, and family – it is easier for children to be influenced and adapt these roles (Webster & Brown, 2019). The society use these gender roles to assign a specific career on a particular sex. Since female are viewed as caring and soft, society thinks that they are suited to work on a caring job (Tabassum & Nayak, 2021). So, they tend to lean on the humanities, communications, and other careers that require caring nature. On the other hand, since males are expected to be strong and technical, they tend to pursue a degree related to science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (OECD, 2012).

In line with this, in a study that aims to investigate and explore the career choice motivation among Library and Information Science students in Tamil Nadu, India, it is proved that most of the students personally chose librarianship as a career choice and genuinely like the library field. The majority of the 277 students from six universities in

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Tamil Nadu were female and in the age group below 23 years. The study's results revealed that location was not a determining factor that motivates or demotivates the career choice but sex, learning mode, and age group plays a vital role (Govindajaran & Dhanavandan, 2018).

Gender Stereotype in Librarianship

Just like with any other career choice or program choices, and as mentioned earlier, society sees Library and Information Science related career as “women’s work,” and anyone associated with it must be female or feminine. It is also revealed that gender roles have negative impact to male librarians as participants expected what they play in the society, such as being the protector and doing physical labor in the library, which added stereotypical image for librarians in general (Blackburn, 2015). Additionally, the gender differences in the perception of librarianship are evident as the male gender perceives the librarians as research experts. However, the female students did not agree with that. The female gender saw the library profession as stereotyped and dull profession with limited job prospects (Funmilayo, 2015). Contrary to the study conducted by Saini & Singh (2018) with a respondent of 92 LIS students, it was found out that 65.2% were male, 33.7% were female and the remaining 1% did not prefer to say their gender. It was revealed that respondents who took Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) as their program were fully aware of the course and were interested in the philosophy of librarianship (Saini & Singh, 2018). Moreover, gender created a stereotype regarding the roles of a librarian in their expertise, when, in fact, a librarian must be equipped with skills and knowledge to fully practice the art of librarianship regarding of what their gender is.

Students' Perception and Knowledge of the LIS Program, Librarians, and the Librarianship Profession

Admittedly, the course Bachelor in Library and Information Science is unfamiliar to most people, most especially to students, resulting in different perceptions and lack of understanding of the course. In a survey on the students' perception of the program, most students associate the course with the word information and library. Also, it was ranked as one of the least valuable professions to society (Kurbanoğlu, Ünal, Tanackoviæ, & Žilić, 2018). Making it a bit low on the potential career choice lists of students. This is further proved by Abban (2019), who utilized stratified sampling to select 353 students from the population of 3533 in Akropong-Akuapem Municipality. He had found that students have a low level of awareness of the librarianship and lacked understanding of said profession – the role librarians play in the society and environment and the specifications and responsibilities of the job. All of these resulted in none of the students having librarianship as one of their career options. Many perceive librarianship to be boring, thus, their lack of interest. Some already have plans for their future careers, like being a doctor, a lawyer, and many others. There are a few percentage who will give librarianship a thought because of their love for books but that is just a small percentage compared to the entire selected sample. (Abban, Choosing Librarianship as Career: A Study of Selected Senior High School (SHS) Students in Akropong- Akuapem Municipality, 2019)

Likewise, as stated in the previous study that Abban spearheaded, they compared nine other professional groups, along with librarianship, and undergoing certain criteria that are considered as factors in selecting a profession, their findings produced results which entails that some students, specifically among those 353 respondents, tested to have low level awareness of the Librarianship profession and lacked understanding of the roles that librarians and libraries play in our society and environment which resulted in

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

different perceptions, which are commonly negative towards the profession and the practitioners (Abban & Reuben, Young People's Perceptions towards Librarians: An Exploratory Study of Students of Five Senior High Schools in Ghana, 2021).

As emphasized in the previous topics and sections of this study, the image, schema, or perception, whichever is appropriate, on the Librarianship Profession and Librarians in general is not that positive. What the students or people see, that is what they understand. In which case, they perceive the job and role of Librarians dull and boring, confined to maintaining of books. Hence, they have a lack of understanding and, of course, awareness of what the program actually entails.

True enough, lack of awareness is due to the lack of information about the library course. There is a lack of young talented people who want to take up this course, and this is related to how the public views libraries and librarians. The responsibilities of librarians are misunderstood. Young individuals may not be aware of other industries or broader information responsibilities because they have likely only used and are familiar with public, school, or university libraries. This causes a lack of understanding of the field and a lack of respect for librarians and their surroundings (Newbutt & Sen, 2009). As a result, there are only a handful of students who have an actual accurate knowledge regarding the program. Although students of both sexes have an average knowledge of the LIS course, when it comes to track/section, STEM students have a superior understanding of the LIS course than TVL students. This is because STEM is more centered on science and math subjects, which encourages frequent library visits and use, whereas the TVL track/section focuses more on improving and developing skills (Lascano, 2021).

Student's Awareness and Motivation on LIS

Many students perceive LIS as something that is boring and is confined to maintaining books or the library collection. The infamy of librarianship program creates a

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wide range of professions. Due to these numerous professions that can be associated with librarianship, it is difficult to identify the people's awareness about the field. It should be emphasized that professional Library Science deals with human knowledge, organization, and access to this knowledge. An area that is very much needed in line with the continuous development of technology. Everyone can find interest in the vast, varied, and fascinating field of librarianship and information studies. With this, the students will be motivated to choose this program (Mugot, 2011).

As stated in earlier parts of this chapter, there is a lack of awareness regarding the program, therefore, there is no clarification on how important it is in the society. In a study that aims to investigate the low preference for library and information science as a first-choice course of study by the undergraduates of Nigerian library schools, the researchers observed that majority of the undergraduates of Nigerian universities apply to study Library and Information Science (LIS) in the first instance but as a last resort. As this study revealed that LIS was not their first choice, it highlighted that despite the evidence of improved popularity of the LIS among the respondents, it remains largely unpopular among prospective undergraduates in Nigeria, when compared to other courses such as accountancy, medicine, and law. This study recommended to strengthen the public awareness about LIS (Issa & Nwalo, 2008).

In another study that aims to raise awareness of careers in the Department of Library and Information Science (LIS), as well as to investigate current awareness and preferences for LIS Department, it reveals that Korean high school students are not aware of the LIS Department and librarians. This study also revealed that the respondents prefer to work at broadcasting library, national libraries, school libraries, university libraries, public libraries, or portals. Lastly, this study showed that awareness of the career path of LIS Department showed an exceptionally significant impact on the respondents'

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

preference for the LIS Department. Therefore, students who have heard and have an idea about the LIS Department are highly probable to select this department when they reach university (Noh, 2015).

In contrast to other professions like doctors, engineers, lawyers, teachers, etc., the library profession is the least popular despite the abundance of resources and the establishment of libraries. The profession of the librarian falls into the category where advanced education is required but is not given much thought by the public (Haining, 2018).

Synthesis

The key point is that, along with some stereotypes with regards to careers or jobs (that is, that there are expected careers for different genders or sex, and different SHS strands), the students or the respondents for each of the studies that the researchers found are not aware, lacked understanding, have a generally negative or biased opinion about librarians, librarianship, and everything related to LIS. There is also the matter of the students' personality that affects their choice in careers, and since the Bachelor in Library and Information Science program or course is usually viewed as boring, women's work, and anything similar to those claims, some students tend to choose other options for careers, especially those careers which are more well-known.

Career decision making and the students' perception are the two parts in which the researchers chose to separate in the study. Career decision making is included because it is a major factor in the level of awareness of the students, particularly, on how the level of awareness of the respondents may affect their career decision making, along with other factors that they take into consideration and other reasons.

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

In a study conducted by Kurbanoglu, Ünal, Tanackoviæ, & Žilić (2018), it is stated that the course Library and Information Science is unfamiliar to most people, most especially to students, thus, resulting in different perceptions, and lack of understanding of the course or program. This study helped the researchers to have a gist of how aware the students are about the librarianship as they conducted a survey on students' perception of the program and majority of the students associate the course with the words *information* and *library*. It was also revealed that librarianship ranked as one of the least valuable professions to society.

There are various studies about career decision making with gender and Senior High School track/strand as apparent factors are apparent and are included in this chapter. Again, gender stereotypes are present in librarianship as it is viewed as women's work, and male librarians are only viewed as only doing physical labor, as stated by Blackburn, without knowing that there is a wide range of professions under and associated to the program as Mugot also states. Various other researches, such as Abban (2019), included in this chapter relates the fact that there is a connection between the perception of students about the profession and their desire to take up the course, either preventing them from understanding it or making them curious about it. Thus, there is a barrier that prevents students from understanding and being aware of the goals and opportunities of the said profession. With the data and information that is to be gathered in this research, it is sufficient and understandable for it to be a basis for a career promotional strategy.

Chapter 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers integrated correlational quantitative research in this study. In constructing the research questions, the researchers took what might be the initial thought of the respondents when hearing about the LIS program into consideration before introducing the course for a little background. The questionnaire contains primary things that the respondents need to know or be aware of as they answer it, such as a brief background of the research, the assurance of the confidentiality of their answers/data, and, finally, the questionnaire proper. The questions stated in the survey is based on the constructed Statement of the Problem from Chapter 1 and should help the researchers better understand the students' perceptions.

The survey questions were based on what the researchers had found from other studies that also focused on the students' level of awareness on the Bachelor in Library and Information Science program. After the students have answered the questions, the researchers analyzed the data gathered. The analyzed data served as a guide to come up with promotional strategies for the aforementioned program.

Population, Techniques and Sample Size

Grade 12 students have a large population. This study used convenience sampling technique. The researchers considered the factors such as time constraints, accessibility, and convenience of respondents and researchers. Therefore, the sample consists of Grade 12 learners from Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Accountancy, Business and Management

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(ABM), ICT, Sports, TVL Maritime, Pre-Baccalaureate Maritime, General Academic Strand (GAS), Agricultural-Fisheries Arts, Home Economics, Industrial Arts, and Arts and Design strands and track, who willingly participated in the data gathering.

Description of the Respondents

Target respondents for this study were the Grade 12 students from different strands during A.Y. 2022-2023. These Grade 12 students came from different schools and universities across the Philippines. According to Department of Education, the strands currently offered are STEM, HUMSS, ABM, ICT, Sports, TVL Maritime, Pre-Baccalaureate Maritime, GAS, Agricultural-Fisheries Arts, Home Economics, Industrial Arts, and Arts and Design.

Research Instrumentation

This research, as stated in previous chapters, observed the level of awareness of students regarding the LIS Program, gauged what they know about it, and checked how it affects their opinions of librarians, the LIS program itself, and the opportunities that comes with this course. The researchers used a structured questionnaire, a combination of a checklist and a rating scale to gather the information needed. These questionnaires were disseminated to Grade 12 students through Microsoft Forms.

The questionnaire consists of five parts: First is the demographic profiles of the respondents, it determined the respondents' strand and sex preference. Then, the second part determined the level of awareness of the respondents about the LIS program and the opportunities upon taking the said course. For part three, their prejudices about the program were determined. The fourth part was about the relationship of level of awareness and taking the course. Lastly, the fifth part identified the respondents' preferred promotional materials. The questionnaire consists of twelve (12) questions which can be answered within five to ten minutes.

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In addition, the researchers used the five-point Likert Scale in the Part two of the research questionnaires. From this, the respondents will specify their level of awareness in five points: (5) Very Aware, (4) Aware, (3) Neither Aware or Unaware, (2) Unaware and (1) Very Unaware.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before collecting the needed data, the researchers humbly requested several library professionals to validate the questionnaires. Once the questionnaire was validated, the researchers conducted a pilot testing on twenty (20) Grade 12 students to analyze the validity of the questionnaire and reliability of the chosen survey method. After getting the results of the pilot testing and making some revisions, the researchers proceeded on the data gathering proper by posting the survey link online. The link was open from December 10 to December 20, 2022, the questionnaire was available within 10 days upon posting the link through social media. Collected responses were treated with the utmost confidentiality. After the survey has been conducted, researchers analyzed the collected data to produce a set of summary and conclusion.

Statistical Treatment

The researchers used various statistical methods to help interpret and analyze the data gathered from Grade 12 senior high school students' response.

1. Percentage frequency distribution

The statistical method is used to determine the percentage and frequency of socio-demographic data and willingness to pursue BLIS gathered from the respondents.

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

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P = percentage

f = frequency

n = number of respondents

2. Mean

This will be used to analyze the results of the Likert Scale on the level of awareness of the respondents about Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) and related career opportunities.

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

Σ = summation

x = level of awareness of grade 12 students about BLIS and related curriculum

n = number of respondents

Likert scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Fully aware
4	3.41-4.20	Slightly aware
3	2.61-3.40	Aware
2	1.81-2.60	Slightly unaware
1	1.00-1.80	Fully unaware

3. Rank-Biserial Correlation Coefficient

If one variable is nominal and the other is ordinal level of measurement, the rank-biserial correlation coefficient can be used to measure association. It is used

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to test if there is any relationship between the level of awareness of Grade 12 students to BLIS and their pursuit of the program.

$$r_{rb} = \frac{2*(y_1 - y_0)}{n}$$

r_{rb} = correlation coefficient

n = number of data pairs in the sample

y_0 = y score means for data pairs with $x = 0$

y_1 = y score means for data pairs with $x = 1$

Legend for Rank-Biserial Correlation Coefficient:

Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation
0.00 to 0.20	Very weak positive/negative
0.20 to 0.40	Weak positive/negative
0.40 to 0.60	Moderate positive/negative
0.60 to 0.80	Strong positive/negative
0.80 to 1.00	Very Strong positive/negative

Chapter 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2: Profile of the Respondents According to Sex

Figure 2 shows that majority of the respondents were female with the percentage of 76% (176 respondents) and the remaining 24% were male (55 respondents).

In line with this, the researchers would like to reiterate the point made by Blackburn, that there were gender stereotypes when it comes to career decision-making and that librarians – or being a librarian is expected as a women’s job. (Blackburn, 2015) From this, it can be easily analyzed that there is a reason that most of the respondents were female. In addition to Blackburn (2015), according to a study conducted by the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), women tend to choose or consider the humanities, communications, and medical fields, or careers that require a caring nature. On the other hand, men tend to choose or consider careers that are science, technology, engineering, and mathematically inclined.

Figure 3: Track/Strand of the Respondents

Figure 3 shows that most respondents were from the Science, Technology, and Engineering (STEM) strand, specifically, 117 respondents. The next highest was from the Accountancy, Business, and Management strand, with 48 respondents. Humanities and Social Sciences came next with 42 respondents. General Academic Strand and Information Technology strands were tied with 10 respondents. Home Economics came last with 1 respondent. The rest of the strands did not have any respondents.

The researchers also confirmed that Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) do not have a specific required track/strand for a student to be enrolled in the course. Additionally, majority of the students as of now, especially those from the same class as the researchers, were also graduated from the STEM strands. As mentioned by Lascano (2021), to reiterate, students of both sexes do have average idea on the librarianship profession or of the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program, but, in comparison, STEM students have more of an idea or a superior understanding of the program/course than TVL students. This is owed to the fact that STEM students and their curriculum, by extension, is focused on science and math,

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prompting frequent library visits or use. Whereas the TVL students and their curriculum focus more on improving and developing skills (Lascano, 2021).

Therefore, there is indeed a connection between the track/strand that students take when it comes to the knowledge about the program.

Table 2.1: Level of Awareness of Grade 12 Students About Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) Program in Terms of Curriculum

Statements	Mean (\bar{x})	Verbal Interpretation
Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) is a board program	2.79	Aware
Students learn skills such as preservation, conservation, and restoration of books and other documents	3.81	Slightly aware
Information technology basics are taught as part of the curriculum	3.46	Slightly aware
Weighted Mean	3.35	Aware

Figure 4.1: Visual Interpretation of Table 2.1

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Figure 4.1 was just a visual representation for Table 2.1 to further understand the table and visualize the respondents' answers.

Table 2.1 shows that the respondents were aware that Bachelor in Library and Information Science is a board program that was supported by a mean of 2.79. The table also shows that the respondents were slightly aware that Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) students learn preservation, conservation, and restoration skills which resulted to 3.81 mean, and that basic information technology is taught as part of the curriculum which was supported by 3.46 mean.

The study by Kurbanoglu, Ünal, Tanackoviae, and Žilić (2018), which focused on the fact that most individuals, particularly students, were not familiar with the Bachelor in Library and Information Science, was similar to the table's findings. The table demonstrated that, despite their preferred professional paths, they were familiar with the program's curriculum. Unfortunately, this resulted to diverse perspective and lack of understanding. The students were therefore familiar with the program but lacked a thorough knowledge of it. This finding supported the study by Abban (2019) that revealed students' lack of knowledge of the course in library and information science and their lack of comprehension of the related profession. Thus, this table shows that in terms of BLIS curriculum, the respondents were just aware of it which resulted to a weighted mean of 3.35. It shows that the Grade 12 students had an idea about it, but they did not fully understand and they did not have a deeper knowledge about the BLIS curriculum.

Table 2.2: Level of Awareness of Grade 12 Students About Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) Program in Terms of Related Career Opportunities (based on CMO 24 s. 2015)

Statements	Mean (\bar{x})	Verbal Interpretation
Abstractor	2.42	Slightly unaware
Academic librarian	4.16	Slightly aware
Acquisitions librarian	3.45	Slightly aware
Archivist	3.26	Aware
Bibliographer	3.7	Slightly aware
Cataloger	3.34	Aware
Corporate librarian	3.54	Slightly aware
Database librarian	3.61	Slightly aware
Documentation officer	3.37	Aware
Indexer	2.9	Aware
Law librarian	3.49	Slightly aware
Library applications developer	3.05	Aware
Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty	3.5	Slightly aware
Map librarian	3.24	Aware
Medical librarian	3.31	Aware
Preservation/ conservation officer	3.1	Aware
Records manager	3.55	Slightly aware
School librarian	4.48	Fully aware
Teacher librarian	4.33	Fully aware
Weighted Mean	3.46	Slightly aware

Figure 4.2: Visual Interpretation of Table 2.2

■ Fully aware
 ■ Slightly aware
 ■ Aware
 ■ Slightly unaware
 ■ Fully unaware

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Table 2.2 shows that Grade 12 respondents were fully aware that a Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) graduate can work as a school librarian, which resulted in a 4.48 mean, and as teacher librarian that has a 4.33 mean.

In addition, in terms of Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) related career opportunities, it shows that the respondents were slightly aware that Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) graduates can work as an academic librarian that was supported by 4.16 mean, as an acquisitions librarian that resulted to 3.45 mean, as a bibliographer that has a mean of 3.70, as a corporate librarian that was supported by a mean of 3.54, as a database librarian which has a mean of 3.61, as law librarian that was backed by 3.49 mean, as a Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty that was supported by a mean of 3.50, lastly, as a records manager which was backed by a mean of 3.55.

Lastly, the table shows that they were also aware about the BLIS related careers such as Archivist, which was supported by 3.26 mean, and Cataloger that resulted to a mean of 3.34.

The table backed up Newbutt and Sen's (2009) study that young people may be unaware of other industries or broader information responsibilities because they have likely only used and are familiar with public, school, or university libraries. As a result, there is a lack of understanding of the field.

Similarly, in the study of Kurbanoglu, Ünal, Tanackoviæ, & Žilić (2018), they emphasized that most people, especially students, were not familiar about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science. The table shows that, despite their preferred choices of career, they were slightly aware of the said program and the career opportunities related to it. However, this resulted to different perspectives and lack of understanding. Hence,

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the students were familiar but lacked the deep understanding of the program. This result also supported the study conducted by Abban (2019) which found out that students had low level of awareness about the Library and Information Science course, and they lacked understanding about the said profession. This includes the roles and responsibilities that the librarians play in society and the specifications of the job. Overall, the data on the table shows that, in terms of related career opportunities, Grade 12 respondents' level of awareness about Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) is 3.45, that is verbally interpreted as slightly aware. It shows that the students have knowledge, but it is not that deep to fully understand and to be fully aware about the said course.

Figure 5: Librarianship-related statements that the respondents agree with.

- Librarians can work in different organizations like hospitals, banks, and schools. (196)
- A Librarian can keep track of every book, whether duplicate or not, in the library. (191)
- Librarians acquire the library collection in a systematic process, Collection Development. (188)

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- BLIS students study how to best handle fragile sources in archives, like original manuscripts. (180)
- Anyone, regardless of gender and age, can be a librarian. (189)
- BLIS program has IT subjects to keep up with modernization and technology. (167)
- Librarians have different job duties and titles. (181)
- A librarian's job is confined to guard and maintain books. (117)
- Libraries and/or librarians are not needed anymore since everything is available for free online. (19)
- Librarians are old women that wear glasses, cardigans, and buns in their hair. (20)
- Librarians can only work in the library. (24)
- Library and Information Science is a dying profession. (60)
- Librarians will just be replaced by computers/artificial intelligence in the future.
- Anyone with a bachelor's degree can work as a librarian. (77)

Figure 5 shows that 85% (196 respondents) of the respondents agreed that librarians can work in different organizations like hospitals, banks, and schools. On the other hand, 83% (191 respondents) agreed that a librarian can keep track of every book, whether duplicate or not, in the library. While the statement wherein it says that librarians acquire the library collection in a systematic process, collection development, 81% (188 respondents) of the respondents agreed. Additionally, 78% (180 respondents) believed that Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) students study how to best handle fragile sources in archives, such as original manuscripts. Anyone, regardless of gender or age, can be a librarian, as per 81% (189 respondents) of the respondents. In addition,

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72% (167 respondents) of respondents agreed that Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program has IT subjects to keep up with modernization and technology.

According to 78% (181 respondents) of the respondents, librarians have different job duties and titles. Fifty-one (51%) (117 respondents) of the respondents also agreed that a librarian's job is confined to guard and maintain books. Meanwhile, only 8% (19 respondents) of the respondents believed that libraries and/or librarians are not needed anymore since everything is available for free online. Furthermore, 9% (20 respondents) of the respondents agreed that librarians are old women that wear glasses, cardigans, and buns in their hair. Aside from that, 10% (24 respondents) of respondents claimed librarians can only work in libraries. Whereas 26% (60 respondents) presumed that Librarianship and Information Science are dying professions. In addition to that, 13% (32 respondents) of the respondents agreed that librarians will just be replaced by computers/artificial intelligence in the future. Lastly, 33% (77 respondents) of the respondents agreed that anyone with a bachelor's degree can work as a librarian.

These results of the survey were consistent with the findings of (Kurbanolu, Ünal, Tanackoviae, & ili, 2018), who revealed that the Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) program is unfamiliar to Grade 12 students, resulting in different perceptions and a lack of understanding of the course.

In line with the study conducted by Mugot (2011), this study revealed that the majority of the respondents with the percentage of 51% (117 respondents) believe that a librarian's job is confined to guard and maintain books.

Figure 6: Respondents considering on pursuing BLIS after answering the questionnaire

Figure 6 shows that, even after some quick information about the course according to the CMO 24 s. 2015, majority of the respondents were not considering BLIS as a career choice in college, more specifically, 68% (157 respondents), whereas there were still those that are considering it, the remaining 32% (74 respondents).

With this data, the argument in the two studies Abban that made can be applied. Many perceived librarianship as boring, which explained their lack of interest in taking the course. Abban also confirmed that students already have their future careers planned out, though there were also those that considered taking the course upon learning some things about the course itself, but there were also a few who would take the course because of their love for books, though it was only a small percentage of the sample (Abban, Choosing Librarianship as Career: A Study of Selected Senior High School (SHS) Students in Akropong- Akuapem Municipality, 2019). Also, Abban and Saah also figured out that people, often, were not aware of the role that librarians play in the society which resulted to different perceptions about the program (Abban & Reuben, Young People's Perceptions

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towards Librarians: An Exploratory Study of Students of Five Senior High Schools in Ghana, 2021).

Lack of knowledge and different perceptions and schema affects the decision of students in at least considering the prospect of pursuing Bachelor in Library and Information Science as a career choice in college.

Table 3: Relationship between the Level of Awareness of the Respondents and their Willingness of Pursuing the Program

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of Awareness	0.096	Very Weak Positive	0.147	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
Willingness of Pursuing the Program					

Table 3 shows a Rank-Biserial Correlation between the respondents' level of awareness and their willingness to pursue the program. As seen in the above table, the test results showed that the correlation coefficient was 0.096 and the p-value was 0.147, which was higher than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is a non-significant correlation between the variables under study. Therefore, level of awareness does not, at any rate, influence the respondents' willingness of pursuing the program.

This result supported Abban's research in which, while there is indeed a correlation in the argument, and there should really be, there were respondents that, even though they learned and or were aware about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science

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course, they already have their own set course choices (Abban, Choosing Librarianship as Career: A Study of Selected Senior High School (SHS) Students in Akropong-Akuapem Municipality, 2019). As continuation of Abban's research, Abban and Saah also argued in a different paper that the students also lacked understanding on how broad and important the course is (Abban & Reuben, 2021).

Additionally, this result also was proven by Lascano's additional argument. It suggested that the respondents were familiar with Library and Information Science (LIS) as a field of study, but they do not view it as a viable option for a career path. This indicates that the respondents do not view LIS as a feasible or desirable choice for pursuing a professional career (Lascano, 2021)

Figure 7: Overall Ranking of students' preferred promotional materials

Figure 7 reiterates the in-depth analysis of how many students chose a certain type of promotional materials and in what order would they rank each given best. According to the results, in Social Media advertisements, 52 students chose it as their 1st choice, 38 their 2nd, 40 their 3rd, 23 their fourth choice, 30 their 5th choice, 31 their 6th choice, 12 their 7th choice, 4 their 8th choice, and 1 their 9th choice.

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

As for seminars, 54 students made it their first choice, 26 their 2nd choice, 23 their third choice, 18 their 4th choice, 36 their 5th choice, 33 their 6th choice, 28 their 7th choice, 13 their 8th choice, while none of the respondents made it their 9th choice.

For webinars, 19 students made it their 1st choice, 49 their 2nd choice, 20 their 3rd choice, 35 their 4th choice, 38 their 5th choice, 34 their 6th choice, 22 their 7th choice, 14 their 8th choice, while none of the respondents made webinar as their 9th choice.

YouTube Contents, meanwhile, had 18 students who chose it as their 1st choice, 30 students their 2nd choice, 46 students their 3rd choice, 32 students their 4th choice, 25 their 5th choice, 14 their 6th choice, 50 their 7th choice, 15 their 8th choice, and 1 respondent made it their 9th choice.

Workplace Tour, on the other hand, had 36 students who chose it as their 1st, 24 students their 2nd choice, 20 their 3rd, 31 their 4th, 23 their 5th choice, 37 their 6th choice, 23 their 7th choice, 33 students chose it as their 8th, and 1 respondent chose it as their 9th choice.

For Brochures, 14 students chose it as their 1st choice, 13 their 2nd choice, 39 their 3rd choice, 46 their 4th choice, 35 their 5th choice, 33 their 6th choice, 28 their 7th choice, 19 their 8th choice, 4 chose it as their 9th choice.

TikTok contents had 30 respondents who chose it as their 1st choice, 40 their 2nd choice, 25 their 3rd choice, 21 their 4th choice, 17 students their 5th choice, 13 students chose it as 6th choice, 16 their 7th choice, 64 their 8th choice, and 5 chose it as their 9th choice.

As for Newsletters, 7 students chose it as their 1st choice, 9 their 2nd choice, 17 their 3rd choice, 23 their 4th choice, 27 their 5th choice, 36 their 6th choice, 50 their 7th choice, 58 their 8th choice, and 4 made it their 9th choice.

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As for the Others option, wherein the respondents were asked to specify their suggested forms of promotional materials/strategies, 1 respondent chose it as their first choice, 2 their 2nd choice, 1 their 3rd choice, 2 their 4th choice, none of the respondents answered it as their 5th or 6th choice, 2 respondents chose it as their 7th choice, 8 students chose it as their 8th choice, and 215 chose it as their 9th choice.

Figure 7 also described and related the ranking positions of suggested promotional materials/strategies that the students would prefer. The first choice was Social Media advertisements – these include all kinds of platforms of social media such as Facebook (posts, reels, etc.), Twitter, and even Instagram. Seminar was the second ranked, followed by its electronic counterpart, Webinars. YouTube Contents came next (this also includes creating a channel and shorts and such as that). Workplace tour came next, followed by a tie between Brochures and TikTok Contents. Newsletters came after these, and lastly, the Others option where the respondents were asked to specify other suggestions of promotional strategies/materials that will best interest the respondents or will they find that should be most helpful in promoting the program. Some suggestions that the respondents specified were infographics, posters, magazines, websites, workshops, short film/story, giveaways, radio advertising, career program orientation, school to school promotions, infomercials, campaigns, promotional merchandise, events, flyers/pamphlets, and tarpaulins and placards.

The respondents best know what they want to see and, therefore, the researchers took into consideration what would appeal to them most when selecting given suggestions for promotional strategies that they believe will introduce or explain the course further to them, indicating that there were some respondents, despite either considering taking the course or not, that would want to see/learn the course, the profession, and librarians in general, in a much understanding light, just like what other similar studies argued or

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defined. Based on the responses of the respondents, and as also mentioned in the previous interpretation and figure, Social Media advertisements was the first choice of the given promotional strategies. Further explanations will be given in the next chapter of this study.

Chapter 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

Overall, the researchers were able to gather data from 231 respondents. According to the results of the survey, in terms of socio-demographic profile, the majority of the respondents were female in terms of sex, and, in terms of SHS strands, most respondents came from the STEM strand. Regarding the level of awareness of grade 12 students about the BLIS in curriculum, the respondents were aware. In addition, they were slightly aware of level of awareness related to career opportunities.

In terms of schema, despite the lack of understanding of the BLIS curriculum and related careers, the respondents had a positive perception of the program and librarianship in general. However, this study showed that, given the chance to learn more about the program, most respondents still did not consider pursuing BLIS. The result of the survey further indicated that the respondents preferred seeing social media advertisements over other promotional materials.

Conclusions

Researchers determined that gender was not a main factor that affected student's knowledge regarding the course; both men and women showed roughly equivalent levels of understanding. With the given findings, the researchers concluded that the STEM track had a higher level of knowledge about the course compared to other tracks. Therefore, students in the STEM track may have more familiarity with the course than students in other tracks. The number of students determined by gender affected their career-decision making. Due to the possibility of females having to pursue careers that requires a caring

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nature, one might consider pursuing Bachelor in Library and Information Science as their option to their choices of career.

In addition, the researchers inferred that the respondents had a low level of awareness about the program. They were aware of the BLIS curriculum; thus, the respondents had an idea about it, but they lacked awareness about the skills and learnings that are taught in it. When it came to its career opportunities, the respondents were slightly aware. Therefore, the respondents were familiar with the program, but lacked deep understanding of the program, the roles, the responsibilities that the librarians play in society.

Over the years, the field has unfortunately been associated with outdated views and ideas, resulting in a lack of recognition of the important work that LIS professionals do. Despite these challenges, the profession is becoming increasingly important in the modern era, with LIS professionals playing a vital role in helping individuals access and make sense of the wealth of information available today. The respondents had positive views or prejudice about the course. Thus, despite having a lack of awareness about Bachelor in Library and Information Science, the respondents were not prejudiced against the program and librarianship in general. Even though they had positive views about the program, this does not directly affect their willingness to pursue this career. The researchers found out that the level of awareness does not directly influence their willingness to pursue the course. It is possible that they lacked the knowledge about the Bachelor in Library Science, but they had already planned their career path based on their tracks, based on their interests, based on their family backgrounds or they do not see the course as a practical and beneficial career as to their preferred ones.

Lastly, the Bachelor in Library and Information Science is a very unknown course to many. People lack awareness about this course; therefore, it needs strategies for

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promotion in order to inform people how vital and in demand this course to the society. The researchers deduced that social media advertisements, in line with the growing technology, is the most appealing promotional strategy. Since most of the people spend their time using it, promotions, and advertisements, it may be graphics, video advertisements, posters, and others, will be more effective if posting through social media platform will be made.

Recommendations

- Showcase some librarians who are also male, and that there are also other career opportunities available for men which are inclined with the BLIS and emphasize that BLIS also does not have a track/strand requirement.
- Promote the program to Senior High School students, especially Grade 12 students, by having activities that can introduce the BLIS program, its curriculum, and possible career opportunities that might pique students' interest.
- Highlight the career opportunities to further prove that there are other specific professions in line with BLIS. Also, feature the responsibilities of being a librarian such as preserving, conserving, restoring a library resource, archiving, and other responsibilities in a library.
- Highlighting the various job prospects related to BLIS can encourage Grade 12 students to consider taking the course.
- Strengthen the promotion of BLIS in different social media platforms by sharing informative contents.
- It is, therefore, recommended that social media be the priority in promoting Bachelor in Library and Information Science according to some opinion on the "Others" option since there are also similar answers that can all boil down to being considered as social media.

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- There are already seminars and webinars conducted in different institutions with a library topic, however, that they are not well-known and/or some are not interested enough in the course/topic to attend them.
- YouTube is also famous for academic content such as Khan Academy and other simple tutorials – a YouTube Channel that will talk about the program and share all about it is recommended as well.
- Workplace Tour is also a good way to advertise the course. It will be effective to eliminate the negative perception of a librarian’s job that is only being confined to guard or maintain books. Additionally, an intervention program similar to a workplace tour may also be implemented – like what some of the respondents suggested in the “Others” option.
- Brochures and newsletters, while in different ranks, may also be explained in an equivalent way. For example, a certain university and institution may create a brochure/newsletter to explain and encourage upcoming students to take the course. They can also utilize this method in announcing or promoting programs and activities that the library is conducting.
- TikTok contents, which can also be related to social media and YouTube, are often used by people for quick tutorials and videos.
- Though, there are many who repeated their answers that had also been mentioned beforehand, there are those that also came up with unique ideas of promoting the course such as infographics, posters, magazines, websites, workshops, short film/story, giving giveaways, radio advertising, career program orientation, school to school promotions, infomercials, campaigns, promotional merchandise, events, flyers/pamphlets, and tarpaulins and placards.

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- The researchers will also attach a project proposal (see Appendix C) that will help put the recommendations into further consideration and help the student organization and the Department of Library and Information Science to consider the study as a basis for future promotional strategies or materials.

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APPENDIX A

Letters

Republic of the Philippines
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Sta. Mesa, Manila

November 25, 2022

Ms. Jacqueline L. Lucero, RL
Chief Librarian
Enderun College
Taguig City

Dear Ma'am:

Greetings!

As part of the requirement in the Bachelor in Library and Information Science Program of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines, the undersigned are required to have an expert validation of the instrument to be used for our thesis entitled "Level of Awareness of Selected Grade 12 Students from PUP Manila about the Librarianship Course and the Opportunities upon Taking This Course: A Basis for Promotional Strategies". In connection with this, we are humbly requesting your assistance to validate our survey questionnaire necessary for the above-mentioned study. Knowing your expertise is most fit and capable to provide such as our expert evaluator.

We have attached here the questionnaire, and the statement of the problem of the study for your reference. We will be glad to hear your suggestions and comments on the improvement of the instrument. Your assistance in this endeavor is vital to complete the above-mentioned research.

Thank you for your time and kind consideration regarding this matter.

Respectfully yours,

Angelica Cameja

Jhylene Capule

Allyson Mae Coloma

Laurice Audrey Cruz

Chineah Dampios

Tricia Ann Rhine De Roxas

Riza Dela Cruz

Noted by:

Dr. Rhodora R. Julian
Chair, DLIS

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Republic of the Philippines
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Sta. Mesa, Manila

November 25, 2022

Ms. Elaine L. Santiago
Librarian II
Angono Municipal Library
Angono City

Dear Ma'am:

Greetings!

As part of the requirement in the Bachelor in Library and Information Science Program of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines, the undersigned are required to have an expert validation of the instrument to be used for our thesis entitled "Level of Awareness of Selected Grade 12 Students from PUP Manila about the Librarianship Course and the Opportunities upon Taking This Course: A Basis for Promotional Strategies". In connection with this, we are humbly requesting your assistance to validate our survey questionnaire necessary for the above-mentioned study. Knowing your expertise is most fit and capable to provide such as our expert evaluator.

We have attached here the questionnaire, and the statement of the problem of the study for your reference. We will be glad to hear your suggestions and comments on the improvement of the instrument. Your assistance in this endeavor is vital to complete the above-mentioned research.

Thank you for your time and kind consideration regarding this matter.

Respectfully yours,

Angelica Cameja

Jhyme Capule

Allyson Mae Coloma

Laurice Audrey Cruz

Chineah Dampios

Tricia Ann Rhine De Roxas

Riza Dela Cruz

Noted by:

Dr. Rhodora R. Julian
Chair, DLI

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Republic of the Philippines
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Sta. Mesa, Manila

November 25, 2022

Ms. Hana Theresa F. Morales
Records Officer I
National Mapping and Resource Information Authority
Taguig City

Dear Ma'am:

Greetings!

As part of the requirement in the Bachelor in Library and Information Science Program of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines, the undersigned are required to have an expert validation of the instrument to be used for our thesis entitled "Level of Awareness of Selected Grade 12 Students from PUP Manila about the Librarianship Course and the Opportunities upon Taking This Course: A Basis for Promotional Strategies". In connection with this, we are humbly requesting your assistance to validate our survey questionnaire necessary for the above-mentioned study. Knowing your expertise is most fit and capable to provide such as our expert evaluator.

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Noted by:

Dr. Rhodora R. Julian
Chair, DLIS

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Republic of the Philippines
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Sta. Mesa, Manila

November 24, 2022

Christine P. Bay
Associate Librarian
Wesleyan College of Manila
Malate Manila

Dear Ma'am:

Greetings!

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Noted by:

Dr. Rhodora R. Julian
Chair, DLIS

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Republic of the Philippines
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Sta. Mesa, Manila

November 24, 2022

Ellaine Cristobal
Library Assistant
Sotero H. Laurel Academic Resource Center, Lyceum of the Philippines University
Manila City

Dear Ma'am:

Greetings!

As part of the requirement in the Bachelor in Library and Information Science Program of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines, the undersigned are required to have an expert validation of the instrument to be used for our thesis entitled "Level of Awareness of Selected Grade 12 Students from PUP Manila about the Librarianship Course and the Opportunities upon Taking This Course: A Basis for Promotional Strategies". In connection with this, we are humbly requesting your assistance to validate our survey questionnaire necessary for the above-mentioned study. Knowing your expertise is most fit and capable to provide such as our expert evaluator.

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Thank you for your time and kind consideration regarding this matter.

Respectfully yours,

 Allyson Mae Coloma		
 Tricia Ann Rhine De Roxas		
 Riza Dela Cruz		

Noted by:

Dr. Rhodora R. Julian
Chair, DLIS

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Republic of the Philippines
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Sta. Mesa, Manila

November 25, 2022

Ms. Lorenza D. Oliveros
Librarian III
City library of Balanga
Bataan City

Dear Ma'am:

Greetings!

As part of the requirement in the Bachelor in Library and Information Science Program of the Polytechnic University of the Philippines, the undersigned are required to have an expert validation of the instrument to be used for our thesis entitled "Level of Awareness of Selected Grade 12 Students from PUP Manila about the Librarianship Course and the Opportunities upon Taking This Course: A Basis for Promotional Strategies". In connection with this, we are humbly requesting your assistance to validate our survey questionnaire necessary for the above-mentioned study. Knowing your expertise is most fit and capable to provide such as our expert evaluator.

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Chineah Dampios

Tricia Ann Rhine De Roxas

Riza Dela Cruz

Noted by:

Dr. Rhodora R. Julian
Chair, DLIS

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Republic of the Philippines
POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF EDUCATION
DEPARTMENT OF LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
Sta. Mesa, Manila

December 5, 2022

Dr. Minna L. Comuyog
Dean, College of Education
Polytechnic University of the Philippines
Sta. Mesa, Manila

Dear Dr. Comuyog:

Greetings!

We, the bona fide Bachelor of Library and Information Science students from the College of Education- Polytechnic University of the Philippines- Sta. Mesa Campus are conducting a study entitled "**Level of Awareness of Selected Grade 12 Students about the Librarianship Course and the Opportunities upon Taking It: A Basis for Promotional Strategies**" as one of the requirements to finish the bachelor's program.

In accordance with the development of the study, we would like to humbly request the number of 1st year enrollees of each program from College of Education from 2018 to 2022. Your assistance to this endeavor is vital to complete the above-mentioned research. We would greatly appreciate your consent at our request.

Thank you for your time and kind consideration regarding this matter.

Respectfully yours,

[Signature]
Angelica Cameja

[Signature]
Jhune Capule

[Signature]
Allyson Mae Coloma

[Signature]
Laurice Audrey Cruz

[Signature]
Chineah Dampios

[Signature]
Tricia Ann Rhine De Roxas

[Signature]
Riza Dela Cruz

Noted by:

[Signature] 12/5/2022
Dr. Rhodora R. Julian
Chair, DLIS

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

APPENDIX B

Survey Questionnaire

Greetings!

We are 4th year Bachelor in Library and Information Science (BLIS) students from the Polytechnic University of the Philippines conducting a research entitled, "**Level of Awareness of Selected Grade 12 Students about Bachelor in Library and Information Science Course and the Opportunities upon Taking it: A Basis for Promotional Strategies**". If you are a grade 12 student this A.Y 2022-2023, your participation in this 5-10 minute survey will be much appreciated. Please answer the questions honestly, and we hope you learn something as you answer this survey questionnaire. All responses will be used solely for research purposes and will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Respectfully,

Cameja, Angelica

Capule, Jhune

Coloma, Allyson Mae

Cruz, Laurice Audrey

Dampios, Chineah

De Roxas, Tricia Ann Rhine

Dela Cruz, Riza

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

I. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Name (optional):

Sex:

Track/Strand:

II. LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS ABOUT BLIS

Direction: Rate your level of awareness in the following statements by ticking the box corresponding your answer.

Fully aware - You have deep understanding of the statement.

Slightly aware - You slightly understand the statement.

Aware - You have an idea about the statement.

Slightly unaware - You are familiar but do not understand the statement.

Fully unaware - You are not familiar nor have an idea about the statement.

1. What is your level of awareness about librarianship in terms of:**a. Bachelor in Library and Information Science curriculum**

	5	4	3	2	1
Bachelor in Library and Information Science is a board course					
Students learn skills such as reservation, conservation, and restoration of books and other documents					
Information technology basics are taught as part of the curriculum					

b. Career opportunities (based on CMO 24 s. 2015)

Bachelor in Library and Information Science graduates can work as:	5	4	3	2	1
Abstractor					
Academic librarian					
Acquisitions librarian					
Archivist					
Bibliographer					
Cataloger					
Corporate librarian					
Database librarian					
Documentation officer					
Indexer					
Law librarian					
Library applications developer					
Library and information science faculty					

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Map librarian					
Medical librarian					
Preservation/conservation officer					
Records manager					
School librarian					
Teacher librarian					

III. PREJUDICE AGAINST BLIS AND RELATED CAREER OPPORTUNITIES

Direction: Check the box beside the statements you agree with.

Librarians can work in different organizations like hospitals, banks, and schools.	
A Librarian can keep track of every book, whether duplicate or not, in the library.	
Librarians acquire the library collection in a systematic process, Collection Development.	
Bachelor in Library and Information Science students study how to best handle fragile sources in archives, like original manuscripts.	
Anyone, regardless of gender and age, can be a librarian.	
Bachelor in Library and Information Science program has IT subjects to keep up with modernization and technology.	
Librarians have different job duties and titles.	
A librarian's job is confined to guard and maintain books.	
Libraries and/or librarians are not needed anymore since everything is available for free online.	
Librarians are old women that wear glasses, cardigans, and buns in their hair.	
Librarians can only work in the libraries.	
Library and Information Science is a dying profession	
Librarians will just be replaced by computers/artificial intelligence in the future.	
Anyone with a bachelor's degree can work as a librarian.	

IV. RELATIONSHIP OF LEVEL OF AWARENESS AND PURSUING THE PROGRAM

1. Given that you will learn more about the program, would you consider pursuing Bachelor in Library and Information Science?

- Yes
- No

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V. PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Directions: Rank the following promotional materials according to what would appeal to you the most.

1. Seminars
2. Webinars
3. Brochures
4. Newsletter
5. Social Media Advertisements
6. Workplace Tour
7. YouTube Channel
8. TikTok Contents
9. Others (Please Specify):

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

APPENDIX C**Project Proposal****The Project Summary**

Proposed Implementing Organization	Department of Library and Information Science Student Organizations and Faculty
---	--

Proposed Project Title	Bachelor in Library and Information Science Program Promotional Materials and Strategies Implementation
Project purpose	To enhance the Level of Awareness of the students and properly know all the aspects that should be known about the program
The context and need for the project	Research measuring the Level of Awareness of Grade 12 students about the Bachelor in Library and Information Science is conducted by some students from BLIS 4-1. The results showed that students still have a lack of awareness about the program in terms of curriculum and related career opportunities, increase and enhance their knowledge about it, especially if the presented promotional strategy or materials will pique their interest and somehow attract their attention.
Evidence	A previously conducted research showed that, although the students are somewhat aware of the Bachelor in Library and Information Science Program, they are not considering taking the program as a career choice in college. In order to both promote the program, encourage students to take the said program, and also debunk some misconceptions about it, an intervention should be done, thus, this proposal about implementing and improving promotional strategies and materials.
Short Project Summary	Activities or strategies that the students answered as something they preferred in the study conducted about this should be the basis of what should be done during the project. Consistent posting of different type of materials and contents showcasing the wonders of BLIS program in different social media platforms, including YouTube and TikTok, to reach more students. Also, conducting a seminar and/or webinar in an interactive or workshop style can encourage students to explore BLIS since they can experience some activities first-hand. Conducting workplace tours either personal or even through videos that can be watched by students can also apply as part of the enhanced promotional strategy.
The Project Beneficiaries	High School Students (especially the undecided ones) - The students will have in depth knowledge about the Bachelor in Library and

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Information Science program and the related career opportunities, which can help them.

BLIS Students and Faculty - Having a concrete promotional plan will help the BLIS students and faculty share the wonders of the program to encourage students to pursue or look into it.

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APPENDIX D

Grammarian Certification

Polytechnic University of the Philippines
College of Education
Department of Library and Information Science
AY: 2022-2023

GRAMMARIAN CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the undersigned has reviewed and been proofread carefully all of the pages of the thesis paper entitled "LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS ABOUT BACHELOR IN LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE COURSE AND THE OPPORTUNITIES UPON TAKING IT: A BASIS FOR PROMOTIONAL STRATEGIES", developed by Angelica Cameja, Jhune Capule, Allyson Mae Coloma, Laurice Audrey Cruz, Chineah Dampios, Tricia Ann Rhine De Roxas, and Riza Dela Cruz, is aligned with the set of structural rules that govern the composition of sentences, phrases, and words in the English language. Also, all corrections and recommendations made have been done and/or incorporated in the final manuscript. This research paper was submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the program Bachelor In Library And Information Science of Polytechnic University of the Philippines - Sta, Mesa, Manila.

Signed this 6th day of March in the year 2023

Signed:

ROCELLE ANNE N. DADUFALZA, MAEd-Eng
Grammarian

APPENDIX

Bionote

Angelica T. Cameja, born on April 29, 2001. She is a college student taking the course Bachelor in Library and Information Science at Polytechnic University of the Philippines. She is known as being well-rounded and aims to become a librarian.

Jhune E. Capule is a graduating College student at Polytechnic University of the Philippines who took Bachelor of Library and information Science. She plans to take the board exam for librarianship to become a licensed librarian.

Allyson Mae Coloma, born on 28th of November 1999. A 4th year Bachelor in Library and Information Science at Polytechnic University of the Philippines. She's currently handling a end-to-end sales process for a twitter based business. After graduating, she plans to take the librarianship licensure examination and get a master's degree in LIS.

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Laurice Audrey D. Cruz, born on January 31, 2000. A graduating student of Bachelor in Library and Information Science from Polytechnic University of the Philippines. She is a mother of 1, but still want to pursue this career by being a licensed librarian and by becoming a librarian in a public or special library.

Chineah Dampios is a student at Polytechnic University of the Philippines, where she took Bachelor in Library and Information Science as her degree program. She is a career-driven student and is planning to take the librarian licensure examination.

Tricia Ann Rhine A. De Roxas, born on February 4, 2001. She is a 4th year college student at Polytechnic University of the Philippines, taking the course Bachelor in Library and Information Science. She currently has writing short stories, reading, playing games, and taking care of her dogs as hobbies. She intends to continue the course and then take the board exam for librarianship. And maybe while working, if given the chance, she will take on another course which is Creative Writing.

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Riza A. Dela Cruz, born on May 20, 2001, is currently a 4th year student in Polytechnic University of the Philippines Sta. Mesa taking Bachelor in Library and Information Science. She currently balances her studies and work and has been a working student all throughout pandemic. She loves listening to music and attending gigs of her favorite music artists. She plays Valorant and other video games during her free time. Career-wise, she plans to complete her undergraduate and pursue a master's degree to advance her career.

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